

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE DIGITAL MARKET ACT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This thesis examines the necessity of implementing a Digital Market Act (DMA) in Uzbekistan, drawing insights from an independent economic report that highlights the dual economic perspective on digital platforms. On one hand, platforms offer significant social and economic welfare gains through network effects, benefiting users and boosting efficiency. However, network effects can also lead to adverse impacts, such as winner-takes-all markets and monopolistic gatekeepers. The DMA is proposed as a solution to strike a balance between preserving efficiency gains and preventing the anti-competitive behavior of the platforms. Besides, this research explores the challenges of implementing the DMA, including distinguishing pro-competitive behavior patterns and narrowing the information gap between regulators and gatekeepers. By analyzing the economic implications of the digital platforms and their network effects, this thesis advocates adopting the DMA in Uzbekistan's digital market to promote fair competition and enhance consumer welfare.

Keywords: Antitrust regulation, DMA, Digital platforms, gatekeepers, Uzbekistan,

Emerging digital platforms has changed Uzbekistan’s economy influencing forms and connection types of businesses. Besides widespread ones like YouTube, TikTok, and Likee, there are other platforms playing a huge role also. Social

networks such as LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter are essential for businesses to reach customers.

In the world of search engines, Google, Yandex, Yahoo, Firefox, and Microsoft Edge are still the big players, influencing customers' choices. Service platforms like Express24, Uzum Tezkor, Yandex Go, and other have made services more convenient. They offer on-demand services and freelance work opportunities, creating jobs and making life easier for people.

People use Android, iOS, and Windows operating systems daily, giving them access to different services and apps. Transactions have evolved easier with platforms like Paynet, Click, Payme, Oson, and Uzum Bank, reaching more people to financial services.

Online marketplaces such as AliExpress, ZoodPay, Texnomart, and Olcha.uz have expanded options for shoppers and supported local businesses to enlarge globally. Communication platforms like Skype, Telegram, Snapchat, Viber, and Line have transformed how individuals communicate and perform jointly.

While digital platforms offer considerable conveniences, they correspondingly fetch challenges. Some platforms can become excessively powerful and hurt competition. Privacy and misinformation are further concerns. The Digital Market Act (DMA) aims to counterbalance between promoting healthy competition and protecting consumers. Current thesis explores how these digital platforms simulate Uzbekistan's economy. By comprehending these effects, we can support the implementation of the DMA to create a fair and prosperous digital market regulation in Uzbekistan.

As of January 1, 2022, the number of subscribers connected to the Internet network in Uzbekistan is about 23 million, marking a significant increase of 15% compared to the corresponding period of 2021. This upward trend in internet users reflects the growing digitalization of society and businesses in Uzbekistan. As the internet user numbers continue to rise each year, it becomes increasingly

crucial to regulate digital platforms through the implementation of the Digital Market Act (DMA) to address potential issues of unfair competition. The rapid growth of digital platforms has undoubtedly brought numerous benefits, empowering individuals, businesses, and the economy as a whole. These platforms have revolutionized the way people communicate, transact, and access information. They have facilitated e-commerce, enabled convenient on-demand services, and fostered new job opportunities through freelance platforms. Moreover, the availability of digital financial services has enhanced financial inclusion and accessibility for a broader segment of the population.

However, along with these advantages, challenges have emerged. Some digital platforms have garnered significant market power, potentially leading to monopolistic behavior and hindering fair competition. The winner-takes-all phenomenon has resulted in dominant players gaining substantial control over their respective markets, potentially stifling innovation and limiting choices for consumers and businesses. Additionally, concerns surrounding data privacy and misinformation on digital platforms need to be addressed. The vast amount of personal data has raised data protection and user privacy questions. Misinformation and the spread of fake news on social media platforms can also have adverse effects on public discourse and social well-being.

It is essential to balance promoting healthy competition and safeguarding consumer rights and interests to ensure a fair and prosperous digital market in Uzbekistan. The DMA delivers a prospect to establish a regulatory framework that encourages innovation, competition, and consumer protection. By imposing clear guidelines and restrictions on the behavior of digital platforms, the DMA can mitigate the negative impacts of market dominance and foster an environment where multiple players can thrive.

Among the key provisions that the DMA could include are:

1. **Prohibition of Unfair Business Practices:** At the core of the DMA lies a commitment to address anti-competitive behaviors that may arise from the

dominant market position of the digital platforms. Provisions aimed at prohibiting unfair business practices, such as predatory pricing, exclusive agreements, and self-preferencing, can play a pivotal role in creating a level playing field for all participants in the digital market. By curbing predatory pricing strategies designed to drive competitors out of the market, the DMA can ensure healthy competition and foster innovation among diverse market players. Furthermore, preventing platforms from exclusive agreements that restrict other businesses' access to essential services can encourage a more inclusive and open digital ecosystem. Additionally, tackling self-preferencing practices, wherein platforms prioritize their own products or services over others, can mitigate the risk of stifling innovation and limiting consumer choice.

2. Data Privacy and Protection: As the flow of data fuels the digital economy, robust data protection measures are imperative to maintain user trust and confidence in digital platforms. The DMA can lay the groundwork for comprehensive data privacy regulations, requiring platforms to handle user data responsibly, transparently, and in compliance with rigorous privacy standards. By empowering users with more control over their personal information, the DMA can grant them the autonomy to make informed decisions about data sharing and usage. Transparent data handling practices and stringent consent mechanisms can enable users to understand how their data is processed and shared, while clear guidelines on data retention and deletion can prevent unwarranted data accumulation. An effective DMA can establish a robust framework for data breach notification, compelling platforms to promptly inform users and authorities in case of security incidents, bolstering accountability and responsiveness.

3. Transparency and Accountability: Transparency is paramount in fostering trust between digital platforms, users, and regulators. The DMA can mandate greater transparency in the operations of digital platforms, algorithmic decision-making, and content moderation policies. By shedding light on the functioning of algorithms that influence user experiences and content visibility, the DMA can

help prevent discriminatory practices and ensure that platforms operate fairly and impartially. Furthermore, transparent content moderation policies can enable users to better understand how their content aligns with platform guidelines, promoting a more open and accountable digital environment. By establishing clear guidelines for platform reporting and auditing, the DMA can facilitate continuous evaluation of platform practices, helping identify potential areas for improvement and adherence to regulatory standards.

4. **Market Monitoring and Enforcement:** An effective DMA requires robust mechanisms for monitoring the digital market and enforcing compliance with regulatory provisions. A dedicated digital regulator with specialized expertise can be entrusted with overseeing platform behavior and market dynamics. Regular market studies and audits can offer valuable insights into potential violations and market trends, guiding timely interventions to maintain a competitive landscape. To incentivize compliance, the DMA can institute a range of fines and penalties for non-compliance, with increasing severity for repeated offenses. Moreover, accessible and user-friendly complaint mechanisms can empower consumers and businesses to report potential violations and seek redress, ensuring a responsive and effective enforcement process.

5. **Consumer Protection:** Prioritizing consumer welfare is a central pillar of the DMA. The Act can prioritize clear and accessible presentation of terms and conditions, ensuring that users are fully informed about the rights and responsibilities associated with digital services. Granting users the right to data portability can facilitate competition by enabling seamless data transfer between platforms, enhancing user choice and control. By establishing efficient redress mechanisms, the DMA can provide consumers with a reliable avenue for dispute resolution, protecting them against unfair practices and reinforcing their confidence in the digital market.

In conclusion, the Digital Market Act (DMA) emerges as a necessary and powerful tool to navigate the rapidly evolving landscape of digital platforms in

Uzbekistan. The insights drawn from an independent economic report highlight the dual economic perspective on these platforms, emphasizing their potential for social and economic welfare gains through network effects while acknowledging the risks of winner-takes-all markets and monopolistic gatekeepers. The DMA, as proposed, presents a well-crafted solution to strike a delicate balance between preserving efficiency gains and curbing anti-competitive platform behavior. The rise of digital platforms has undoubtedly transformed the way people connect and conduct business in Uzbekistan. From social networks to search engines, service platforms, and online marketplaces, the digital ecosystem has brought forth numerous benefits, empowering individuals, businesses, and the economy as a whole. E-commerce, on-demand services, freelance opportunities, and digital financial services have enhanced accessibility, convenience, and financial inclusion for millions. However, as these platforms expand their influence, challenges emerge that warrant attention and regulatory action. Some platforms have acquired significant market power, potentially leading to monopolistic behavior that stifles competition and limits choices for consumers and businesses. Additionally, data privacy concerns and misinformation on digital platforms necessitate robust measures to protect user information and ensure transparent operations. It is crucial to maintain trust and accountability among digital platforms, users, and regulators to foster a vibrant and equitable digital market.

By thoughtfully implementing the DMA, Uzbekistan can capitalize on the immense potential of digital platforms while mitigating the risks associated with market concentration and unfair practices. This thesis advocates for the adoption of the DMA to create a fair and prosperous digital market that supports economic growth, fosters innovation, and safeguards consumer interests. Through comprehensive analysis, collaborative policymaking, and effective enforcement, the DMA can become a critical catalyst in shaping Uzbekistan's digital future. The growing number of internet users reflects the country's increasing digitalization,

reinforcing the urgency of regulating digital platforms through the DMA to address potential issues of market concentration and unfair practices.

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